

Accelerating the development of low-cost diagnostics through Responsible AI and open science based innovations

Mboalab's contribution to the local manufacturing of Point of Care Testing (POCT)

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The Mboalab is an open and collaborative space created in December 2017 in Yaoundé, Cameroon. The aim of our collaborative space is to catalyze sustainable local development through open science based innovation. By choosing education and R&D in health as the priority axes, Mboalab has notably contributed to improving healthcare. Indeed, the Mboalab research and production laboratories tackle prevalent diseases such as malaria, cholera, and typhoid fever by developing low-cost diagnostic methods and cost effectiveness reagents, while training local researchers and students on cutting-edge technologies. At the Mboalab, the open science-based innovation is rooted in three domains : Synthetic Biology, Artificial Intelligence and digital fabrication.

Artificial Intelligence applied to Health (AI4Health)

Mboalab endeavors to revolutionize disease diagnosis through the integration of AI technology, reshaping infectious disease screening, overcoming barriers of accessibility and accuracy. Some of our projects are:

- *Improving cancer treatment efficacy and reducing overtreatment by providing a rapid and highly sensitive diagnostic tool.* Utilizing digital microscopy and telepathology, we propose a hybrid diagnostic method using deep learning algorithms on histology slides¹.
- *The Open-Disease Screener* utilizes microscopy of clinical specimens for rapid and cost-effective diagnosis of infectious diseases².

Digital fabrication

Mboalab's exploration into 3D printing technology exemplifies the convergence of innovation and accessibility, and helps to transform healthcare delivery in low-resource settings^{3,4,5}. with projects like the:

¹ <https://github.com/jafsia/Breast-Cancer-Diagnostics>

² <https://github.com/Mboalab/Open-Diseases-Screener-App>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-00956-6>.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03193-5>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2023.0257>

- *open-source wireless 3D printed Digital Stethoscope*⁶;
- *OpenFlexure, an open-source 3D printed optical microscope*, integrating high-precision mechanical positioning technology and AI.

Synthetic biology

Over the past five years, the focus at Mboalab has extended to developing contextualized protocols and applying cost-effective manufacturing methods for local enzyme production in Cameroon. Simultaneously, we established Mboalab Biotech with the mission to make Innovation and biotechnology research tools more accessible to people and organizations in Cameroon and Africa. As a pioneer in protein production in Cameroon and the first company to establish a complete manufacturing and R&D unit in the country, Mboalab Biotech has played a pivotal role in the development of the local biotechnology sector⁷⁸⁹.

Mboalab's commitment to leveraging AI in low-cost diagnostics has been listed by the International Research Centre on AI (IRCAI) under UNESCO's auspices, in the 2022-23 edition of the Global Top 100 AI projects addressing the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Our Partners

⁶ <https://github.com/Mboalab/Digital-Stethoscope-Project>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0252507>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpz1.387>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.02.20.580892>